

ANALYSIS OF THE SINGLE-FIBRE PULL-OUT TEST FOR ARAMID/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The single-fibre pull-out test has been analysed for Kevlar 49 fibres in a cold-cured epoxy resin using Raman spectroscopy which has been employed to determine the distribution of fibre strain in the pull-out test by mapping the variation of strain along an aramid fibre undergoing pull-out from the epoxy resin matrix. A partial debonding theory has also been developed to explain the pull-out behaviour in such a system. It is shown that the fibre strain distribution can be modelled fully using the partial-debonding model allowing the interfacial parameters to be determined with a high degree of precision.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely acknowledged that the fibre/matrix interface influences the properties of fibre-reinforced polymer composites. In general, fibre-reinforced composites should possess a good interfacial shear strength, τ_s , that is dependent upon the fibre surface properties and the mechanical properties of the fibre and matrix. Several test methods have been developed for the evaluation of τ_s including fibre fragmentation [1-3], push-out or indentation [4], and the single-fibre pull-out test [5,6]. The different techniques yield different results and correlations between them are often poor [7,8]. The single-fibre pull-out test is, however, a method commonly employed for the determination of the interfacial parameters because of its simplicity and versatility. Unfortunately, the data reduction schemes that are normally employed to analyse single-fibre pull-out data are not reliable since the distributions of fibre strain in the test-pieces are not known accurately enough.

This study uses Raman spectroscopy to quantify the strain distribution along a Kevlar fibre, of embedded length $\sim 1000 \mu\text{m}$, undergoing pull-out from an epoxy resin matrix. The process is also analysed theoretically using a modified theory that combines conventional shear-lag analysis [9] and debonding theories [10]. This theory is used to model the partially-debonded single fibre undergoing pull-out and so determine both the interfacial shear strength for failure of the fibre/matrix interface and the interfacial frictional shear stress for fibre pull-out. It is demonstrated that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful method of following the micromechanics of fibre deformation in composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fibre used in this study was a commercial grade of aramid fibre, Kevlar 49 supplied by E.I. Du Pont de Nemours, Central Research, Wilmington, USA. The fibres had been sized during processing to improve both the handling characteristics and matrix adhesion in composites. They had a diameter of $\sim 12 \mu\text{m}$, a tensile modulus of about 120 GPa, a tensile strength of $\sim 2.6 \text{ GPa}$ and a strain to failure of about 2.2%. The matrix material was a two part, cold-curing epoxy resin consisting of 100 parts by weight of butane-1,4-diol diglycidyl ether resin (LY5052) and 38 parts by weight of isophorone diamine hardener (HY5052), both obtained from Ciba Geigy. It has a Young's modulus of about 3 GPa and a shear yield stress of $\sim 43 \text{ MPa}$.

The single-fibre pull-out (SFPO) specimens were prepared using silicon rubber moulds approximately 10 mm square by 3 mm deep as described elsewhere [11]. Specimens were prepared with a range of embedded lengths from 100 μm to 1500 μm and a free fibre length of approximately 40 mm.

Raman spectra were obtained from the aramid fibres, both in air and within the epoxy resin, using the 632.8 nm red line of a 15 mW helium-neon laser focused to a 5 μm spot on the surface of the fibre. A highly-sensitive Wright Instruments charge-coupled device (CDD) camera was used to collect Raman spectra using an exposure time of 7 seconds. The peak position of the strain sensitive 1610 cm^{-1} Raman band [11] was used to map the fibre strain profiles at various levels of applied strain.

CONVENTIONAL ANALYSIS OF PULL-OUT

The shape of the force/displacement curves obtained from the pull-out test depends ultimately on the intrinsic characteristics of the interface and on the dynamics of the test. In general, for brittle fibre/resin systems, three types of curves are commonly observed (Figures 1(a-c)). In the first case (Figure 1(a)), for very strongly-bonded interfaces or weak interfaces where the embedded length is very small, the stored energy within the system is high enough to immediately extract the fibre after the initiation of interfacial failure, and only the maximum force during pull-out can be recorded. If the testing guidelines [9,12] are implemented the second type of curve (Figure 1(b)) may be obtained [13], although it is more commonly observed with weakly-bonded interfaces. In this case, after interfacial failure, the fibre may be extracted progressively and frictional pull-out monitored until final failure. Such data yield not only the maximum pull-out load but also the frictional load on the fibre. The third type of curve (Figure 1(c)) has been observed by Penn and Lee [14] for Kevlar/epoxy, and by Takaku and Arridge [15]. Penn and Lee attributed the peaks in the ascending region of the force/displacement curve to damage caused by friction as the debonded region develops along the fibre/matrix interface. Takaku and Arridge, however, proposed a step-wise debonding phenomenon.

Figure 1. Schematic illustrations of possible force-displacement curves for the single-fibre pull-out test.

The pull-out test is analysed conventionally from the relationship between the maximum pull-out load, F_p^{\max} , and the embedded length, L_e . Early analyses of these types of data [16] assumed a yielding interface that would allow the shear stress distribution along the fibre/matrix interface to be approximated as a constant, τ_a , which is defined through the simple force balance equation for a fibre of radius, r :

$$F_p^{\max} = 2\pi r L_e \tau_a \quad (1)$$

The determination of τ_a from the experimental data in this manner ignores stress concentrations and is therefore normally referred to as a "mean apparent interfacial shear strength" [17].

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS OF PULL-OUT

Piggott [9] has analysed *elastic stress transfer* for a pull-out specimen with one end of the fibre embedded in a resin block and the fibre gripped at the point where it leaves the resin such that there is no free length ($L_f=0$). Application of a strain to the fibre, ϵ_{app} , in order to extract the fibre (embedded length L_e) from the polymer matrix creates a strain distribution within the embedded region of the fibre, ϵ_f , that declines with a distance x from the polymer surface according to the equation [10]

$$\epsilon_f = \epsilon_{app} \frac{\sinh[n(L_e - x)/r]}{\sinh [ns]} \quad (2)$$

where s is the fibre aspect ratio L_e/r and

$$n^2 = \frac{E_m}{E_f} \frac{1}{\ln(R/r)} \frac{1}{(1+\nu_m)} \quad (3)$$

$\ln(R/r)$ can be considered to be a volume fraction parameter. The corresponding interfacial shear stress is obtained from the consideration of the equilibrium of forces exerted on a differential fibre element of length dx [18]:

$$\tau = E_f \frac{d\epsilon_f}{dx} \frac{r}{2} \quad (4)$$

Differentiation of Equation 2 and substitution into Equation 4 yields:

$$\tau = \frac{n}{2} E_f \epsilon_{app} \frac{\cosh [n(L_e - x)/r]}{\sinh [ns]} \quad (5)$$

The *debonding model* proposed by Piggott [10] assumes a constant interfacial shear stress, $\tau = \tau_i$, and for a pull-out specimen for which the interface fails by debonding the integration of the balance of forces [18] yields:

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{2\tau_i}{rE_f} (L_e - x) \quad (6)$$

The assumption of a constant shear stress gives

$$\tau = \tau_i \quad (7)$$

where τ_i is known as the interfacial frictional shear stress, related to the radial pressure, P , exerted on the fibre by the matrix and the interfacial coefficient of friction, μ , by $\tau_i = -\mu P$.

The elastic and debonding theories proposed by Piggott [9,10] can be modified to model the partial debonding behaviour of single fibre composites. For the totally-debonded situation Equation 6 assumes that at a distance $x=L_c$ the strain in the fibre is zero. However in the partially debonded case, the assumption that the strain distribution in the debonded region is defined by the embedded length is not valid. From Raman strain profiles it is clear that the linear decrease in strain in the debonded region is defined by an imaginary point $x=z$ (Figure 2). Equation 6 then becomes

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{2\tau_i(z-x)}{rE_f} \quad (8)$$

In the fragmentation test Piggott assumed that debonding occurred over a distance $mL_c/2$ from the fibre ends, with $0 < m < 1$. For an epoxy/Kevlar(sized) pull-out specimen consisting of a single fibre in an epoxy resin block, debonding would be expected to initiate at the polymer surface ($x=0$) where the fibre enters the resin [19]. It can therefore be assumed that debonding occurs over a distance $(1-m)L_c$ from the polymer surface. In the zone of perfect adhesion, Equation 2 and the continuity of axial stress at $x=(1-m)L_c$ yield

$$\varepsilon_f = \frac{2\tau_i}{rE_f} [z-(1-m)L_c] \frac{\sinh [n(mL_c-x)/r]}{\sinh [nms]} \quad (9)$$

Differentiating Equation 9 and substituting into Equation 4 yields

$$\tau = \frac{n\tau_i}{r} [z-(1-m)L_c] \frac{\cosh [n(mL_c-x)/r]}{\sinh [nms]} \quad (10)$$

Equations 9 and 10 define the axial strain, and interfacial shear stress distributions in the region of the composite where there is no debonding. The corresponding distributions in the debonded region are given by Equations 8 and 7 respectively.

The total applied strain required to partially debond a fibre, ε_{app} , is given by the sum of the frictional (debonded) and frictionless (bonded) components of the partial debonding model as shown in Figure 2. Assuming the frictional shear stress to be constant, the axial strain component in the debonded region is given as:

$$\varepsilon_f^{deb} = \frac{2\tau_i(1-m)L_c}{E_f r} \quad (11)$$

The axial strain contribution from the bonded region is controlled primarily by the interfacial shear strength, τ_s , and the embedded length L_c . At the initiation of debonding at $x=mL_c=0$ Equation 9 gives the strain in the debonded region for $m=1$ as:

$$\varepsilon_f^{bon} = \frac{2\tau_s}{nE_f} \tanh[nms] \quad (12)$$

Therefore the total strain required to partially debond a fibre by a length of $(1-m)L_c$ is

$$\epsilon_f^{\text{tot}} = \epsilon_f^{\text{deb}} + \epsilon_f^{\text{bon}} = \frac{2\tau_s}{nE_f} \tanh[nms] + \frac{2\tau_i(1-m)L_c}{E_f r} \quad (13)$$

Figure 2. Theoretical plots for partial debonding during pull-out for the Kevlar 49/epoxy system using the various parameters indicated.

From the partial debonding theory it is possible to define a constant in the form of a critical length, L_{crit} . It is the distance of a propagating debond from the fibre embedded end for which the debonding will become unstable and lead to a substantial load drop in the force displacement curve. It therefore controls the maximum strain, ϵ_f^{max} , that is obtained during pull-out. The transition from stable to unstable debonding occurs when the derivative of the total stress, σ_f^{tot} , with respect to the bonded length, $(1-m)L_c$, is less than or equal to zero [20]. For our convenience we have used the derivative of the strain with respect to the bonded length, i.e.

$$\frac{d\epsilon_f^{\text{tot}}}{d(1-m)L_c} \leq 0 \quad (14)$$

The solution yields for the critical condition

$$L_{crit} = mL_c = r \frac{\cosh^{-1}[\sqrt{(\tau_s/\tau_i)}]}{n} \quad (15)$$

The critical bond length is a constant for a given composite system being dependent on the ratio of E_m/E_f , the fibre/matrix volume fraction, the frictional shear stress τ_i and the interfacial shear strength τ_s . The critical bond length also defines the maximum strain, ϵ_f^{max} , obtained during a pull-out experiment for a given embedded length. Hence for $L_e > L_{crit}$

For a single fibre composite with $L_c < L_{crit}$ the maximum strain during a pull-out experiment is observed at the initiation of debonding ($m=1$) and so from Equation 12

$$\epsilon_f^{max} = \frac{2\tau_s}{nE_f} \tanh[ns] \quad (17)$$

For a given composite system there will be a maximum embedded length of fibre, L_c^{max} , that can be debonded and 'pulled-out' from its matrix without the fibre breaking at its failure strain (ϵ_f^*). The value of L_c^{max} is obtained by equating the solution for the maximum debond strain (Equation 16) to the ultimate tensile strain of the fibre, ϵ_f^* , and it is given by

$$L_c^{max} = \frac{rE_f}{2\tau_i} \left[\epsilon_f^* - \frac{2\tau_s}{nE_f} \tanh \left[\frac{nL_{crit}}{r} \right] + \frac{2\tau_i L_{crit}}{E_f r} \right] \quad (18)$$

Equations 16, 17 and 18 allow the application of the partial debonding model to the conventional mechanical pull-out test.

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Figure 3 shows the distributions of strain along the Kevlar 49 fibre of embedded length $L_c=1080 \mu\text{m}$, for nominal applied strains, ranging from 0.6% to 1.6%. This single Raman experiment provides a detailed insight into the three stages of pull-out: namely

- (i) elastic deformation, (ii) partial debonding, and (iii) frictional pull-out.

It should be pointed out that a nominal strain, ϵ_0 , will be employed to generate the theoretical curves for the Raman data. The nominal strain is the estimated maximum strain in the fibre at the surface of the resin ($x=0$). The value of ϵ_0 may vary slightly from the applied strain, ϵ_{app} , in the free fibre due to the stress concentration where the fibres enter the resin block.

At low nominal strain, $\epsilon_0 \leq 0.60\%$, the fibre strain decreases from a maximum where the fibre enters the resin to approximately zero at the fibre embedded end. Figure 3 reveals that this behaviour is quantitatively similar to the distribution of fibre strain predicted by shear lag theory [9]. The slight discrepancy between the theoretical curve given by Equation 2 and the experimental data at $x > 200 \mu\text{m}$ may be a result of residual compressive stresses on the fibre induced during curing of the resin matrix.

At increased nominal strains, $\epsilon_0 \geq 0.60\%$, (Figure 3) the simple shear-lag theory becomes inadequate to model the corresponding strain distributions. It is apparent from Figure 3 that debonding at the fibre/matrix interface has occurred and the distribution of strain is now defined by two distinct zones. The debonded and bonded zones can be defined by the continuity of axial strain at the point $x=(1-m)L_c$ and the limits $x=0$ and $x=L_c$. Taking suitable values for m and z to fit the experimental data, the theoretical strain distributions can be generated from Equations 8 and 9 for a given nominal strain. As the strain is increased there is stable propagation of the debond along the fibre/matrix interface. The correlation between the experimental data and the theoretical strain distributions are very good for all partially debonded data (Figure 3).

Once the fibre has been completely debonded from the matrix the pull-out process is controlled by interfacial friction and the strain profile in the fibre is given simply by Equation 6. From the experimental results it was observed that the fibre pulled-out in a 'stick slip' manner and it was only possible to obtain two strain profiles of the debonded fibre. It can be seen that the experimental data in Figure 3 fit well to straight lines except for $x < 50 \mu\text{m}$ where there is a slight discontinuity in fibre stress [11] as discussed earlier.

Figure 3. Variation of fibre strain with distance along the fibre at different levels of applied strain, ϵ_{app} , determined using Raman Spectroscopy.

The interfacial shear stress distributions can be derived through Equation 4 from the theoretical curves fitted to the fibre strain profiles in Figure 3 generated from the theory [21]. In the totally-bonded condition, as the applied strain is increased the maximum interfacial shear stress increases until debonding is initiated. At nominal strains above 0.60% debonding is initiated and propagates along the interface as the strain is increased. The interfacial shear stress builds up from the fibre end and then reaches a peak value of between 32 and 42 MPa at which point debonding occurs [21]. The interfacial shear stress in the debonded region is of the order of 5 MPa and remarkably constant. It would appear therefore that the interface has a maximum shear strength, τ_{max} , of the order of 42 MPa which is approximately equal to the shear yield strength of the epoxy matrix ($\tau_y = 43 \text{ MPa}$) [22]. Assuming that debonding of the fibre/matrix interface occurs when the yield stress of the matrix is reached, then for the composite system investigated it follows that $\tau_{max} \approx \tau_y \approx \tau_{deb} = \tau_s$.

Following total debonding of the fibre and the onset of frictional pull-out the value of τ_i increases to 5.3 MPa and then at $L_e = 600 \mu\text{m}$ to 7.5 MPa [21]. One possible explanation is the resistance to motion of kink bands and other regions of irregular fibre diameter. The fibre can then behave as a string containing knots along its length. As pull-out proceeds these knots cause an increase in debris around the interface increasing roughness and consequently increased friction [23].

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that Raman spectroscopy is a powerful tool for the investigation of interfacial phenomena in composites. Application of the technique to the single fibre pull-out test combined with the development of a partial debonding theory have led to the conclusion that the initiation of fibre debonding is controlled primarily by the interfacial shear strength, τ_s , for a given composite system. The partial debonding model for single fibre pull-out adequately describes the strain profiles obtained from Raman spectroscopy at all levels of applied strain. Furthermore, propagation of fibre debonding and the subsequent extraction of the fibre from the resin matrix are controlled by the interfacial frictional shear stress, τ_f , which is unique to a particular pull-out specimen.

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